

REPORT:

A4.1.2: Selection of physical and biological quantities

Work package 4

2025-11-15

<https://mfmet.eu>

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A4.1.2 M5	Based on A4.1.1 outputs, FOG with the support from UTwente, CEA, CETIAT, IPQ and ALU-FR will perform a documented selection including both physical and biological quantities. Quantities and ranges will be selected based on a comparison of the participants' (CEA, CETIAT, IPQ, ALU-FR) testing capabilities, end-users needs collected in A4.1.1, and 20NRM02 MFMET's outcomes. This work will be done in parallel with A1.2.1, A1.3.1, A2.2.1, A2.3.1 and A3.3.1 to ensure that the developed setups are compatible with their envisioned protocols when possible. The report from A1.1.1 will be used in this activity.	FOG , UTwente, CEA, CETIAT, IPQ, ALU-FR
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1. Scope

This document provides a documented selection of both physical and biological quantities of interest in order to define the set functional and metrological requirements of the setup to be developed and qualified within MFMETII WP4.

2. Selection process

To select relevant physical and biological quantities, the following process has been followed:

- a) From MFMETII A4.1.1, collect end-users and stakeholders' needs in term of physical and biological quantities of interest
- b) Collect partners testing and measurement capabilities for physical and biological quantities of interest for microfluidics / organ-on-a-chip applications related to a).
- c) Select common quantities in a) and b) for which at least two partners have the testing and measurement capability
- d) Check the compliance of c) outputs with MFMET and MFMETII activities: selected quantities from c) shall be discussed/addressed in MFMET and/or MFMETII reports or deliverables.

2.1. A4.1.1 outputs

2.1.1. Physical quantities survey from MFMET

Surveys and interviews conducted within MFMET project led to the following physical quantities and ranges of interest identification:

Figure 1: identification of physical quantities of interest from MFMET project surveys

Figure 2: flow rates ranges of interest from MFMET project survey

Figure 3: requested flow control accuracy from MFMET project survey

Figure 4: operational pressure of interest from MFMET project survey

2.1.2. Biological quantities survey from MFMETII

A survey conducted in MFMETII A4.1.1 led to the following identification of biological quantities of interest:

Average Score by Biological Quantity

Figure 5: biological quantities of interest from MFMETII A4.1.1 survey

2.2. Partners capabilities

The following table presents the collection of MFMETII participants' capabilities related to A4.1.1 outputs (see section 2.1).

Table 1: participants' capabilities related to A4.1.1 outputs

Partner	Quantity	Range	Uncertainty (k=2)	Details/ reference
CEA	Cell viability	Using Calcein live/dead staining. 0-100 %		
	Cell confluency	0-100%		
	Biocompatibility	Of devices rather than materials. Based on viability		
	Sterilization	Pass/Fail		
CETIAT	Liquid flow	1 nL/min to 1 mL/h	2 to 30 %	CMC in BIPM KCDB
	Liquid velocity	0,1 to 100 $\mu\text{m/s}$	negligible	Traceability ensured
	Pressure, pressure drop	0 to 8 bar	TBD	Traceability ensured
	Flow resistance	0,1 to 1 TPa.s/m ³	0,15 TPa.s/m ³	From flow and pressure
	Contact angle	0 to 180 °	1°	Traceability ensured
	Surface energy	50 to 100 mN/m	25 mN/m	From contact angle and traceable standard liquids
	Particle counting	TBD	TBD	
	Total volume, dead volume	1 μL to 100 μL	0,6 μL	From traceable weight
IPQ	Contact angle	0 ° to 108 °	1 to 8 %	Wilhelmy plate method
	Shear stress	TBD	TBD	Rheometer, new method. Determined using the shear viscosity definition, as the ratio of shear stress and corresponding shear rate.
	Flow rate	0,0003 mL/h to 2000 mL/h	2,7% to 0,1 %	CMC in BIPM KCDB
	Flow velocity	Variable, depending on tubes and capillaries diameters.		
	Flow resistance / pressure drop	0,1 to 1 TPa.s/m ³	0,15 TPa.s/m ³	From flow and pressure
	Total volume, dead volume	0,1 μL to 10000 μL	5 to 0.1%	CMC in BIPM KCDB
	Pressure, pressure drop	0 to 10 bar	0,01bar	Traceability ensured
	Particle counting	TBD	TBD	Use of high resolution camera to count and follow the particles
ALU-FR	Flow	70 to 200 nL/min	TBD	
UTwente	Cell Viability (live/dead staining)	0-100%		
	Cell Confluency (imaging)	0-100%		
	Ad/absorption	Depends on target	Depends on target	Using soluble markers
	Cell Layer Leakage/Permiability	Depends on assay	Depends on assay	
	Biocompatibility			ISO 10993-5 Method
	Sterilization	Pass/Fail	Pass/Fail	
	particle count			Multisizer 4e coulter counter
	flow	100 nL/min-40mL/min	~5% but depends on range	Large range of commercial sensors available in-house

				(Bronkhorst, Fluigent Etc.)
	Pressure/burst pressure	1 mbar – 100 bar		Large range of pressure sources available from 1 mbar to 100s of bar.
	Flow resistance			See above two details.

2.3. Compliance with MFMET outcomes and MFMETII activities

According to section 2 steps c) and d), the following quantities are selected and their compliance with MFMET and MFMETII activities, reports and/or deliverables is assessed:

Table 2: compliance of selected quantities

Partners / Quantities	Physical	Biological	In A1.1.1 report?	In MFMET reports?
CEA, CETIAT, IPQ	Contact angle		No	Yes (Deliverable D4)
UTwente, IPQ, CETIAT	Liquid flow / velocity		Yes (velocity, §2.3)	Yes (flow, A.2.2.2 §2.3, Deliv. D3)
UTwente, IPQ, CETIAT	Pressure / pressure drop / flow resistance		No, but in A1.2.1	Yes (A.2.2.2 §2, deliverable D3)
CETIAT, IPQ, UTwente	Particle counting		Yes (§2.5)	No
CEA, UTwente		Cell viability	No, but addressed in A4.1.1 surveys	
CEA, UTwente		Cell confluency		
CEA, UTwente		Biocompatibility		
CEA, UTwente		Sterilization		

3. Selected physical and biological quantities

The following table summarizes the physical quantities selected and their measurement ranges, based on partners capabilities and A4.1.1 outcomes:

Table 3: selected physical quantities and their ranges

Quantity	Ranges
Contact angle	0° to 180°
Liquid flow / velocity	1 nl/min to 100 µl/min
Pressure / pressure drop / flow resistance	0 to 8 bar / 0.1 to 1 TPa.s/m ³
Particle counting	Depends on particle sizes, channel dimensions and flow rate

The following table summarizes the biological quantities selected and their specific parameters, based on partners capabilities and A4.1.1 outcomes:

Table 4: selected biological quantities and their parameters

Quantity	Parameters
Cell viability	Using Calcein live/dead staining. 0-100 %
Biocompatibility	Of devices rather than materials. Based on viability